

Interview with Anime Director Naomi Nakayama at FicZone 2025

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Naomi Nakayama —中山奈緒美— is a multifaceted artist and Japanese animation director with a solid career in the anime industry. She began as a writer and storyboard artist on prominent series such as *Casshern Sins*, *Iron Man*, and *X-Men*, evolving into directing productions like *Hunter × Hunter*, *Orange*, and *Sword Art Online*.

Naomi Nakayama, artist and director

In 2024, she took on the role of director for the seventh season of *My Hero Academia*, replacing Masahiro Mukai —marking a new creative direction for the adaptation. Nakayama also directed the anime *Koikimo* (2021), produced by Nomad. As a storyboard artist, she contributed to titles such as *Sword Art Online*, *Re:Zero*, *Carole & Tuesday*, and *My Hero Academia*, standing out for her narrative clarity and visual dynamism. Her ability to combine direction and drawing makes her an all-around creator, a key figure in the new generation of modern anime.

She has worked at Madhouse alongside artists like Ai Yokoyama, whom we also interviewed and with whom she maintains a friendly and professional relationship; we had the opportunity to meet both during FicZone 2025.

Interview with Naomi Nakayama

Cool Japan: You have worked in action series such as *My Hero Academia* as well as more emotionally-driven stories like *Orange*. How do you decide the appropriate tone for each project? Both for ensemble projects and intimate stories. What challenges does each type of narrative present from a director's perspective?

Naomi Nakayama: When directing, it is easier to work with fewer characters because this allows you to delve into the plot, but that was my first job and I had very few characters. *Orange* was my first series as a director [not only of individual episodes, but the complete series]. When there are few characters, you have to express how they feel, how they have grown and developed, how they think.

I learned from this experience, so now I can use it to coordinate an ensemble story with many more characters.

CJ: Speaking of *My Hero Academia*, is there any episode that has particularly marked you, either emotionally or technically?

NN: In *My Hero Academia*, I really like Toga-chan [Himiko Toga]. I also really like the story in which Toga and Ochaco [Ochaco Uraraka] fight, at the end of the seventh season... what a season!

The scene referenced by Nakayama-san

CJ: You were also involved in projects such as the Marvel comics anime adaptations and *Hunter × Hunter*. How has your style evolved since then?

Naomi Nakayama: We were both at Madhouse [referring to Ai Yokoyama, whom we also interviewed at FicZone 2025], working on animations for audiences outside Japan. I do a lot of work aimed at international audiences, and as I was a newcomer, that's how I trained. So... if I had to put it simply, I'm better at that style which is well received abroad. I think this experience has been very positive for me.

Sketches of Izuku Midoriya by Naomi Nakayama, created to commemorate the finale of *Boku no Hero*.

CJ: Is there any genre or topic you haven't explored yet that you would like to tackle in the future?

NN: In terms of work? I love action anime, so I really enjoy shōnen with lots of battles, but... what would I like to do in the future? Well, I'd like to do something tough like *Hard Boiled* [1992 film directed by John Woo]; and something like *Vampire Hunter D* [referring to *Bloodlust*, 2000] that Yokoyama-san [Ai Yokoyama] mentioned. I'd like to combine the best of both styles.

CJ: Do you have any special routine or process when starting a new project? How do you immerse yourself in the atmosphere of a story?

NN: Hmm... I read books and watch films, and I think a lot about images I like from my favourite scenes, and I use this in my work. At the beginning of any project there is free time, and I use that time for this. For example, if I like a scene I've seen, I make a drawing, and think, "I want to work in this direction."

So I make what's called a mood board, where I include many images I want to use for my work and keep them. Basically, I do this first and then start working on various things.

CJ: Many fans in Europe follow your work. What does it mean for you to be able to share your vision with an international audience?

NN: I don't just think about the Japanese audience, but also America, Europe... I'm happy that young people around the world see my work and give their feedback. It makes me very happy. I don't just want this to happen in Japan; I want people to find my work interesting wherever it goes.

That's what I aim for, so I'm very glad to receive comments from people abroad on social media saying my work was entertaining. It really encourages me!

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Additionally, Nakayama-san kindly recorded a greeting for CoolJapan.es, which you can watch via this [YouTube link](#)!

Sources

- **Texts consulted from:** Official FicZone website, Anibase, Anime News Network | **Interview conducted by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es] | **Interview interpreted by:** Michie Yamaya
- **Images sourced from:** Official FicZone website, Anibase, Tumblr

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